

Shaping the rules of the game: Spanish capitalism and the publishing industry under dictatorship (1939-1975)

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This article examines the development of Spanish capitalism under Franco's dictatorship (1939-1975) through the interaction between two major actors: the book publishing industry, a fast growing and internationally minded sector, and the Spanish Government. We argue that Spanish publishers, by defending their interests and redefining their strategies in an extremely restrictive and vulnerable environment, strengthened their coordinating capacities while shaping Spain's economic institutions. The main conclusion of this empirical study is that engaged and/or legitimacy seeking actors can effectively contribute to change the rules of the economic game. We contend that this ability of entrepreneurial actors to shape the rules over time needs to be better integrated into the VOC theoretical framework.

Institutions have recently regained a central role in the social sciences. Why are some institutions good for economic growth and social welfare and others not? Why do some countries endow themselves with adequate institutions while others are apparently unable to do so? The temptation to classify countries according to the quality of their institutions is as old as industrial capitalism itself. Nevertheless, at the beginning of the 21st century, political scientists Peter Hall and David Soskice proposed a theoretical framework, the comparative institutional advantage, to identify and analyze the different types of capitalism prevalent in the most advanced economies of the world (Hall and Soskice, 2001). The varieties of capitalism (VoC) approach, initially limited to liberal market economies (LMEs) and coordinated market economies (CMEs), has been a source of inspiration for the social sciences to this day.

This article seeks to advance in that direction using the tools of business history and borrowing many ideas from the *Business History Review* "Varieties of Capitalism" Roundtable. This paper examines the role of private firms in the institutional design of capitalist systems from a historical and institutional perspective. We explore how the rules of the game changed in Spain and the role played by two actors: entrepreneurs and Government. The interest of the former to grow and gain new markets and of the latter to survive and obtain international recognition would lead them to support each other

and coordinate their interests/efforts, thereby contributing to changing the rules of Spanish capitalism. Our research covers the decades 1940s, 1950s, and 1960s, 1970s, i.e. the Franco dictatorship. The complete industrialization of the country, with the development of Spanish capitalism, took place during our observation period. We argue that the relevance of the observation period for the Spanish economy, and the changing context through the different phases of the Franco regime, make Spain a perfect laboratory to analyse how institutional changes materialize, and what actors and dynamics influence the process.

The paper focuses on one illustrative case study: the experience of the publishing industry during the Franco period. The evolution of the book publishing industry enables us to follow the track of the Spanish variety of capitalism at a crucial stage for the modernization of the country. A relevant industry since the early twentieth century, publishing grew spectacularly in the national and international markets between 1950 and 1975 and has ranked among the top ten worldwide ever since. How and why interact these two actors? To what extent did their coordination capacities transform the institutional arrangements inherited or imposed by the political objectives of Franco's regime and international isolation?

The editors of this volume affirm that the development of the varieties of capitalism is the result of the complex interaction between Government and entrepreneurs over time and in different contexts. We want to verify this by analyzing the Spanish publishing sector on a solid empirical basis that allows us to identify the interests and strategies of both actors, and evaluate their impact on the economic performance of the firms and Spain's political economy. Our intention here has been to avoid the merely formal or legal analysis of institutions, or the interpretation of these as entities isolated from society. For this reason, part of our effort in this research has been dedicated to reconstructing the interest groups that existed within the industry and their relationships with the public administration, in the hope of contributing to the debate regarding the influence of these groups on decision-making and, ultimately, on economic development (see, for example, McCraw, 1997; Fellman et al. 2008). In this way, the paper will allow us to make a twofold contribution to this Special Issue: an empirically sound understanding of the active role of entrepreneurs and firms in the shaping of national business systems through stable coalitions, and a historically informed analysis of the specific impact of such coalitions on the evolution of the industry.

Our research is based on four governmental archives (General Administration Archive, Ministry of Finance, Bank of Spain, and Spanish Book National Institute), and five corporate archives (Gustavo Gili, Salvat, Espasa Calpe, Urquijo Bank Archive, and

Industrial Credit Bank). We have also examined the periodical publications *El Libro Español* (1958 to 1975), *Anuario Financiero y de Sociedades Anónimas*, the census of the book publishing industry and the register of publishing companies. To improve our understanding of the interaction between business and Government and the dynamics of informal networks, we have relied on personal interviews, autobiographies and memoirs.

The paper is organized as follows. The first section is a brief overview of previous literature on Spanish capitalism. The second section presents the institutional context, the Spanish political and economic situation during the Franco regime. The next three sections show the central part of the research: the presentation of the actors (entrepreneurs and government), and the relation between them. The following sections present the new legal and fiscal framework, and the impact on the publishing industry. The final section explain our main conclusions.

SPANISH CAPITALISM IN HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

Before the formalization of the debate about VoC by Hall and Soskice in 2001, its main hypothesis and underlying ideas already constituted a central topic in business history literature (Wilkins et al. 2010). A defining moment was the publication of Alfred D. Chandler's book, *Scale and Scope*, in 1990. The book encouraged scholars from all over the world to test the advances of US-style managerial capitalism in their research countries (Chandler, 1990). The Spanish case was addressed by Albert Carreras, Xavier Tafunell and Eugenio Torres, who determined that until the 1980s the Chandlerian model had made little progress in Spain. They argued that the persistence of small family businesses and the ubiquity of the State made it difficult to develop economies of scale and the multidivisional firm (Carreras and Tafunell, 1997; Carreras, Tafunell and Torres, 1997). Spanish business historians then turned their attention to explain the persistence of family capitalism and trust-based relationships, noting that large family firms and entrepreneurial families, in fact, have led the modernization and internationalization of the Spanish firm between the 1970s and 2008 (Fernández Pérez and Puig, 2007; Puig and Fernández, 2008).

In Spain, however, attention to the (mostly negative) peculiarities of indigenous capitalism rose long before Chandler's works. A generation of economists and sociologists as prolific as influential took care of it since the nineteen sixties. The economists Juan Velarde and Enrique Fuentes Quintana, among many others, pointed out that a strong presence of the State and the resulting extreme regulation that hindered

competition, had consolidated in the Spanish institutional framework, notwithstanding the frequent turns in the country's economic policy since the beginning of the industrialization (Velarde, 2009; Fuentes Quintana, 2009). At the same time, the Spanish born sociologist at Yale University Juan Linz and his numerous disciples put the focus on Spanish corporatism, more specifically on the ability or tendency of governments and businessmen to coordinate their interests during the years of accelerated industrial growth (1960-1975) and the democratic transition (1975-1982). These researchers were struck by the ability of the State, in Spain and in Southern Europe in general, to reach lasting agreements with employers and workers, as well as the formation or transformation of often parapublic associations (Linz, 1983).

A later generation of political scientists influenced by Hall and Soskice's research have applied the VoC paradigm to the Spanish case, focusing on the institutional adaptation to the market economy, to the European Union and to globalization. The most explicit analysis was conducted by Sebastián Royo (Royo 2002, 2007). This author is interested in the development of coordination capacities in the field of industrial relations, a process that depends on the organization, interests and strategies of the Administration, employers and unions. Institutions would be therefore designed and redesigned through a dynamic process influenced by the environment as much as by the social actors. Certain exogenous shocks and historical circumstances, argues this political scientist, can exert a lot of pressure on the actors, accelerating change. Our article falls in this debate. It makes use of the VoC specific framework, proposed by Hall and Soskice, to understand institutional changes during the Franco regime. We also consider Royo's works on Spanish capitalism, and his exhortation to study "the logic of the social actors' strategies" (Royo, 2007, 61). By doing so, our paper focuses on the interaction between publishers and Government, and its probable impact on Spanish capitalism.

SPAIN'S INSTITUTIONAL CONTEXT

The final victory of the nationalist military in the Spanish Civil War (1936-1939) would lead to almost four decades of dictatorship. The previous literature has divided Franco's dictatorship into two periods. The first covers the years between 1939 and 1959, when Spain –isolated in the international context– was still constrained by autarkic economic policies. During this period, the new regime tried to guide the economy with a set of anti-market policies that resulted in high inflation rates, the development of black markets and a substantial reduction of international trade. The turning point would come in November of 1950, when the United Nations and the United States began to dialogue

with Franco. The support of the US administration for Spain was a key factor in breaking down international isolation and building economic confidence within the country, thus helping to perpetuate Franco's power (Calvo-Gonzalez, 2007). From 1950 onwards, the Government would change its economic strategy, introducing successive pro-market changes, relaxing its control over the economy and loosening its extreme interventionist policies. As the coercive power of the State decreased, economic recovery began.

The second period began in 1959 (Townson, 2007). The adoption of the Stabilization and Liberalization Plan (Plan de Estabilización y Liberalización) signalled a new phase in Spanish economic development. A new Government of technocrats elaborated the plan, which included important liberalization measures and a conventional stabilization programme to control inflation and public spending, as well as promote market liberalization and international market integration. The practical aspect took primacy over the ideological and the State took a step back from its original postulates. The 1960s would be a decade of intensive economic growth and the country's complete industrialization. During these years, Spain was experiencing its own "golden age", in line with the considerable economic growth taking place in other capitalist countries (Martín Aceña and Martínez Ruiz, 2007).

The nation's industrial policy would have to wait until this second, post-1959, phase. The tools designed by the Franco Government to accelerate industrialization were known as the Development Plans. Three such plans were implemented: the first from 1964 to 1967; the second from 1969 to 1971; and the third from 1972 to 1975. They established incentive programmes for industrial investment, priority sectors, poles of growth, export subsidies and a series of other measures to stimulate business. In imitation of the central planning designed by De Gaulle in France, Spain's Development Plans were quadrennial and contained a series of targets or projected milestones that, although not of obligatory compliance for private companies, were indeed compulsory for public entities. Industry thus grew at a greater speed than other sectors and spearheaded the structural transformation of the economy. This institutional context, at first autarkic, then liberalizing, but always tinged with interventionism, would condition the dynamics of the country's business fabric (De la Torre, 2005; Fernández Pérez, 2006; Torres Villanueva, 2003; Valdaliso Gago, 2007).

During the 1960s, Spain underwent a sound social and economic transformation led by a new generation of brilliant engineers and recently graduated economists usually referred to as "the technocrats". Inspired and supported by international institutions such as IMF and OECE, these professionals used their newly reached positions of power within the post-1959 Spanish Government to challenge the economic ideas that had been

hegemonic during the two previous decades (Caballero Miguez, 2008). Without questioning the political structure of Franco's regime, the technocrats implemented more rational and free-market policies that revealed their permeability to the business community and paved the way for administrative reform and economic growth. This new environment favoured the rise of a reformist faction within the regime that would play a crucial role in the Spanish democratic transition (1975-1982) (Palomares, 2007).

THE ACTORS (I): THE ENTREPRENEURS

The Spanish publishing sector was not born during the Franco era. From the late 19th century through the early 20th century, Spain had boasted an important book industry, with a strong presence in Latin America (Larraz Elorriaga, 2007; Martínez Rus, 2008). It was in that period that Spanish publishers, restricted by a limited national market, had decided to begin exporting their books. In the principal destination for Spain's publishing output, Argentina, market share for Spanish publishers in the imported book market was 41% in the period 1911-1914 and 47% in the period between 1915 and 1919 (General Administration Archive, Foreign Affairs, Boxes 447 and 463). Market shares for Spanish publishers were also high in Cuba (48%), Peru (30%), Panama (8%), Chile (19%) and Nicaragua (10%) (Martínez Rus, 2002).

Spanish companies did not receive any governmental support to assist them in this pioneering internationalization process. Moreover, Spanish trade associations would develop later than those in other European countries such as France, Germany or Great Britain. The Official Chambers of the Book, in Barcelona and Madrid, were created in 1918 and 1922, respectively (Sanchez, Martínez Rus, Martínez, 2004). Their performance was uneven, but the Catalan Chamber of the Book was exceptionally active in terms of internationalization. For our study, however, it is important to note that these business associations would set the tone for Spanish associationism within the publishing sector, constituting an important legacy from this earlier phase and a determinant for understanding the behavior of the industry during our own period of study.

In the 1920s, the average for Spanish book exportation of 39% of total production (Gili, 1944). For companies such as Salvat and Gustavo Gili, this rose to over 50% (Gustavo Gili and Salvat Archives). One-off or on-demand exportation evolved over time into a firm process of internationalization in the 1920s and 30s, with title adaptation and foreign direct investment. Unfortunately, the Spanish Civil War would put an end to this promising phenomenon. The war and post-war period were catastrophic for the publishing sector, as the country's disastrous economic situation, together with

restrictions of production due to shortages of energy and raw materials, combined to plunge the industry into a profound crisis. If, during the war, Spanish publishing exports had totalled 39% of production, by the mid-1940s this had fallen to less than 10%, while the number of publishers even capable of exporting had decreased as well (Fernández Moya, 2012).

Added to the problems common to other industries within the Spanish business panorama, the publishing sector would suffer a more singular problem: the exile of a great many publishing professionals and intellectuals. Indeed, many of the prime movers of the sector's pre-war transformation would be forced into self-exile for their connections with the Republican cause (Larraz Elorriaga, 2009 and 2010). In business terms, this exile had two negative consequences for the Spanish publishing sector. First, it was in effect "orphaned" by the disappearance of many of its most important figures and entities. Second, the publishing sectors of Mexico and Argentina, countries in which many Spanish exiles settled, were consequently strengthened (De Diego, 2006). The new companies that arose on the other side of the Atlantic would become the main competitors of Spain's publishing houses in the middle decades of the 20th century.

The evolution of the publishing sector, in terms of company size and capitalization, paralleled that of the general Spanish economic context. However, the available documentary sources, according to their nature and objective, offer only disparate quantitative data regarding the development of the Spanish publishing sector in the Franco era. In 1945, the *Anuario financiero y de sociedades anónimas* recorded a total of 142 companies for the entire graphic arts sector (*Anuario financiero y de sociedades anónimas*, 1945/46, 296). The economic recovery of the 1950s is reflected in an increase in the number of *sociedades anónimas* (limited liability companies) registered, which in 1960 already comprised 303 companies (*Anuario financiero y de sociedades anónimas*, 1960/61, XLVII). The developmentalism of the 1960s is also reflected in the figures presented in the *Anuario*. In 1965, 406 *sociedades anónimas* were registered for the graphic arts sector (*Anuario financiero y de sociedades anónimas*, 1965/66, XLVII). In 1970, this would reach 506 and, at the end of the Franco era (1975), 611 (*Anuario financiero y de sociedades anónimas*, 1975/76, XXIV).

The second documentary source, the census of the publishing sector, shows much higher figures. In 1945, the census listed a total of 290 publishers, forming a category independent from the rest of the graphic arts and press sector (Martínez Martín, 2015b, 234). In the 1950s, the number of publishers in Spain fluctuated between 550 and 600 companies (Martínez Martín, 2015b, 253). A third source, the Register of Publishing Companies, within the Spanish Book National Institute (INLE, by its acronym in

Spanish), bears witness to the sector's dynamism in the later years of the Francoist era. From 1966 to 1975, a total of 1,920 companies would apply for inscription in the Register (Martínez Martín, 2015c, 275). All of the documentary sources reveal a clear tendency: this was toward growth, beginning in the 1950s and becoming notably heightened in the 1960s. However, the disparity of these figures indicates that the publishing sector was still comprised mostly of small-sized businesses, some of only intermittent activity and publishing a meagre number of titles annually. The legal status of *sociedad anónima* was reserved for the sector's more prominent publishers, understood as being those with the largest sales volumes.

From these sectoral statistics, we are able to distinguish three types of companies. The first were the historical market leaders, for their size and revenue, which had been founded in the early 20th century and had gained experience and knowledge in both domestic and foreign markets. This was the case of companies like Espasa Calpe, Aguilar, Gustavo Gili, Sopena, Labor and Salvat. The second were new publishers that, although still young and small in size, had been born with the ambition to scale the ranks of the domestic publishing sector and developed aggressive growth strategies to do so. Some of these remain in operation today, such as Planeta (founded in 1949 and currently the eighth largest publisher in the world), Taurus (1954), Plaza y Janés (1959), Anaya (1959), Seix Barral (1954), Santillana (1960), Alfaguara (1964), Alianza (1966), Anagrama (1969) and Tusquets (1969). The third group was comprised of smaller, lesser known companies, created sometimes by an individual entrepreneur. Operating with low capital, their activity was circumscribed to a specific line of publishing in which they specialized, a strategy which enabled them to survive in the market. Barcelona and Madrid continued to be the two great poles of the industry, with 44% of publishers having their headquarters in Madrid and 30% in Barcelona.

Our research reveals that Spanish book publishers were fully integrated into the international industry through their active participation in international associations. Spanish publishers also began to attend international fairs. Statistics for the 1962 Frankfurt Fair (the most important world publishing event) show that of the publishers in attendance, 171 were Spanish, 81 German, 68 French, 39 American, 28 Swiss, 23 Dutch, 6 Mexican and 6 Argentinian (General Administration Archive, Culture Section, Box 73-000475, Report "España pierde su mercado en América Latina", Sept. 1962). The 14th annual International Publishers Conference was held in Barcelona in 1962. Santiago Salvat Espasa, company owner and a leading figure in the Catalan publishing industry of this period, served as president of the International Publishers Association from 1962 to 1966 (Fernández Moya, 2010).

On the supply side, the number of companies and their productive capacity increased. The technical modernization of the graphic arts sector, beginning in 1950, would bring about the latter development. As for demand, the advances that were then taking place in educational level and purchasing power must be noted. Illiteracy rates dropped considerably; in 1940, 23% of the Spanish population was illiterate, a figure that would fall to 14.2% in 1950, 11.2% in 1960 and 8.5% in 1970. The rise in scholarization in the 1960s was greatly marked at the secondary and higher educational levels, with the number of secondary school students growing by 159% and that of university students by 142% (Martínez Martín, 2015 c, 278). Growth rate in GDP in the 1940s was 1.37%, rising to 5.43% from 1950 to 1958 and reaching 6.92% in the period between 1958 and 1974 (Prados de la Escosura, 2003,133 and 151) This increase would occur in parallel to increased consumption and investment in books. This is shown by the data in the following table:

Table 1
Investment per capita in books, 1966-1971
(in pesetas)

Year	Investment per capita in books
1966	386.97
1967	444.93
1968	553.46
1969	655.86
1970	800.36
1971	1,046.50

Source: Cedán Pazos (1972), taken from Martín Sánchez (2015), p. 411.

As for financing, the publishing sector was comprised mainly of family-run companies or individual entrepreneurs who had created their enterprises with minimal resources of their own. Business people and companies in other sectors had no interest in publishing, either as investors or as managers.

THE ACTORS (II): THE GOVERNMENT

For the entire duration of the Franco regime, the State would play a central role in driving the publishing sector forward. Political institutions that were involved in some way in the production and sale of books included: the National Paper, Press and Graphic Arts Union, the Council of Spanish Culture, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Ministry of National Education and the Vice-Secretariat of Popular Education and Propaganda Services. To provide an outlet for publications aligned with the regime, the *Editora Nacional* (National Publishing House) was created in 1941. This publicly owned entity was charged with combining commercial criteria with objectives of propaganda (General Administration Archive, Culture Section, Boxes 66-20615 and 66-20349). However, the greatest tutelary exponent of the Franco Government in this area would be the Spanish Book National Institute (INLE, by its acronym in Spanish).

The INLE was an entity modelled on the Republican Spanish Book Institute, and classed as an autonomous body depending on the Ministry of the Interior's Sub-Secretariat of Press and Propaganda. The Institute arose from the Ministerial Order of 23 May, 1939, as the "central body of consultation and management for all issues relative to the production and distribution of Spanish books". As such, the INLE exercised the functions of: managing the domestic and foreign policies of the Spanish book; promoting propaganda through competitions, festivals, fairs, expositions and contests; organizing Spain's representation in international assemblies and conferences related to books; proposing and drafting norms designed to combat illicit competition; publishing a bibliographical bulletin of Spanish-language books; and editing the General Catalogue of the Spanish and Latin American Book Industry (Cedán Pazos, 1969, 43-44). That is to say, the INLE was given the functions which before the Civil War had been carried out by the official Book Chambers of Madrid and Barcelona before the Civil War.

After its victory in the Civil War, the new State had first to decide what kind of publishing sector it would allow to exist. In theory, the Government could have either opted for a production monopoly and control the final product in this way, or allow private enterprise and exercise control over its output. As for the type of books published, its dilemma in the postwar period was whether the *blue book*, which exalted the values of the State and propagated its message, should be the only one authorized, or whether the *commercial book* should also be permitted (Martínez Martín, 2015 a, 33). We have no documentary record of the existence of any open debate on the possibility of channelling publishing output through a monopoly, something which would have been difficult in any case. This was the idea, however, which underpinned the formation of the *Editora Nacional* in 1941, as practicality took precedence over ideals (García Naharro, 2015). It is true that in the postwar period, the Spanish publishing sector found itself in dire

straits, but it carried with it a considerable historical legacy that would aid its speedy recovery. Companies like Salvat, Gustavo Gili and Espasa Calpe were the heavyweights of the publishing industry; the State, unable to ignore this reality, chose to respect the actions of the private publishing sector, while marking its legal limits and supervising its production.

The most visible aspect of the Franco Government's control was censorship. In the year 1939, an iron-fisted censorship board was established within the Nationalist administration. The so-called "Serrano Suñer" law brought into being a system of censor approval under which all published works had to be reviewed before they were released onto the market (Ruiz Bautista, 2015). Publishers were required to send their publication plans semi-annually to this board for Government approval. Changes in Spanish society and in the power structure of the regime itself would lead to the modification of this legislation in 1966. In that year, a new Press Law went into effect, under the authority of Information Minister Manuel Fraga. The law did away with the previously compulsory censor approval program, at the same time that it heightened state supervision of the publishers themselves. Police files of their biographical details were registered with the INLE, together with the rest of their companies' documentary data. It is important to note that the objective of the new legislation was not to make censorship more flexible or permissive, but rather to better manage a massive bureaucracy that, given the rise in supply and demand, had become a problem for the public administration. The words of Manuel Fraga, who said that the State "must either channel these changes, or be overwhelmed by them", reflect this desire to adapt to the new reality (Menchero de los Ríos, 2015, 69). As with other controlling procedures, censorship was not exercised in a rigorous or systematic way, but rather discretionally (Ruiz Bautista, 2008).

RELATIONS BETWEEN ENTREPRENEURS AND THE GOVERNMENT

Franco's Government limited freedom of movement for entrepreneurs, instead channelling this officially through the "Vertical Unions". In general terms, this system granted very little freedom of operation to the few existing business organizations, thereby reducing their capacity for dealing with the abuses of the State at the same time that State power was increasing (Cabrera y Del Rey, 2011).

Of course, in the case of the publishing sector, the creation of the INLE implied the dissolution of the Book Chambers of Barcelona and Madrid (founded in 1918 and 1922, respectively). However, the publishers soon realized the necessity, or convenience, of dialoguing with the Regime. To do this, the sector needed to be well-structured and

cohesive. The historical chain of events that took place before the Civil War, the legacy of the period addressed in the first section, may explain the early creation of a common front to defend the sector's interests: the National Assembly of Authors, Publishers and Booksellers, founded in 1944.

How was collective action in the sector structured? Its operations were carried out, on the margin of the official orders, by mixing legal activities with illegal ones. The sector's geographical concentration in Madrid and Barcelona would facilitate the process of coordination. Meetings held within the sector but outside the associations stipulated by law, for example, were a frequent but illegal practice. The testimony of Francisco Pérez González, the co-founder of Santillana and a frequent interlocutor with the administration, describes the situation like this:

Here (Madrid), we didn't have a collective feeling as a trade like there was in Barcelona. And I learned many things; I also learned that this legal-illegal system worked, because at the same time that Santiago Salvat (leading publisher) was going to official trade group meetings, there were those meetings going on where decisions were made that they would later apply and I would pass on to Ernesto Antón and to Ignacio Caballero (attendees of the Madrid meetings) (Fundación Germán Sánchez Ruipérez, 2006, 78).

The Barcelona meetings were held, for example, in the offices of Salvat. In Madrid, the premises used for such meetings were the offices of *Selecciones del Reader's Digest* or Espasa Calpe. That is to say, the meetings, however clandestine they might have been, were held in the headquarters of leading publishers who were not markedly anti-Francoist. Indeed, the directors of the various official organisms, including the INLE, knew about and tolerated these type of gatherings.

The actions of the publishers as a pressure group became patent in the revision of the INLE, an entity that had hitherto resisted reform. Initially, the INLE depended on the Vice-Secretariat of Popular Education (Secretariat-General of the Movement). In this first phase, ideology had prevailed over economic considerations. The first president, Julián Pemartín, would justify the Government's actions with bombastic rhetoric. In his understanding, the Institute, unlike the former Chambers, should not support the publishers' commercial activities, but instead redeem the book from its purely commercial character (Rodrigo Echalecu, 2015, 100). This orientation and philosophy was maintained in the years that followed, despite the modification of the public body that supervised the INLE. In 1945, the Institute found itself under the authority of the Directorate General of Propaganda, within the Ministry of National Education. In 1951,

with the creation of the Ministry of Information and, the INLE became dependent on the Directorate General of Information.

In 1957, with the arrival of the technocrats to political power, a deeper reform of the Institute's internal structure took place, aimed at adapting it to the sector's new reality and needs. Joining the INLE's administrative board were various technicians from the public administration, along with influential politicians such as Laureano López Rodó, at that time technical secretary-general of the Presidency, and later to become both a minister and chief officer of the Government's industrial policy.

The reform of 1957 was a turning point in the relations between the publishers and the administration. Initially, the new managers tried to control and guide the workings of the Institute without the consent of the publishers. The publishers, on the other hand, were eager to take an active role in the political and economic transformation of Spain that was then under way. Acting collectively, they sought to approach the highest officials of the Ministries of Information and Tourism and of Trade (Escolar, 1999, 231-235). The publishers had the support of the Secretary-General of the INLE, Eduardo Nolla, who was described as an "intelligent Galician and heterodox Falangist, whose general sympathies were inclined toward solving the publishers' problems" (Escolar, 1999, 231). Finally, at a meeting in El Escorial, they drafted a document in which they formulated their goals and suggested a series of measures favouring the book and the publishing industry. This document was received and supported by Laureano López Rodó, General Manager of the INLE and, as we have already mentioned, a key representative of the new economic policy (Comín and Vallejo, 2009, 140-141). Through his mediation, the Franco Government accepted the demands of the publishers, who then came to form part of both the board of directors, and the general delegated commission of the INLE, the entity's most powerful governmental bodies. This was the first step taken by the publishers toward shaping the institutional framework from within.

After the reform of 1957, the INLE became an official institution with a mixed character, aimed at serving individuals as well as the State. Highly skilled technical personnel were added to the top management of the INLE, including Foreign Trade and Customs officials, as well as private publishers, to help solve the sector's most pressing problems. Archival data supports this affirmation of the dual role played by the INLE. The publishers used the Institute to deal with sectoral issues –and, consequently, to influence Government decisions– and to participate in the application and execution of measures and policies favourable to the industry. Time-honoured Spanish publishers, such as Joaquín Sopena, Victor Seix, Francisco Bruguera and the Salvat brothers, sat on the board of the INLE and its delegated commission and participated in all of its debates.

Their participation was wide-ranging and would affect the handling of the issues which most concerned them.

The Institute was clearly a channel through which they could transmit their complaints and requests to the top officials of the Franco Government's political hierarchy. In the records of the board of directors, it can be clearly seen that these executives proposed measures, participated in the execution of Governmental plans and designed cultural, business and diplomatic initiatives. There were a great number of interactions with the Ministry of Trade, to communicate problems in bilateral trade dealings with some countries and overcome obstacles to the exportation of books, and with the Ministry of Finance to reduce or modify the criteria for some of the taxes levied on publishers. (Bank of Spain Archive, Spanish Institute of Foreign Currency, Box 226, INLE, Agreements 1/64 and 2/64 Board of directors INLE). They tried as well to interfere in the slow and cumbersome system of exportation and currencies, even going beyond the authority of the entity responsible for this, the Spanish Institute of Foreign Currency (IEME, by its acronym in Spanish) (Bank of Spain Archive, Spanish Institute of Foreign Currency, Box 227, INLE General Notes, October 1963, Exports of books).

The publishers, then, had a presence at all levels, and not only on the board of directors. They appointed commissions for various tasks, from organizing expositions to handling tax payments (Bank of Spain Archive, Spanish Institute of Foreign Currency, Boxes 224, 226 and 227). The opening of the INLE's office in Costa Rica, the Institute's only foreign delegation, was proposed the publishers themselves, specifically Santiago Salvat, the owner and director of the company with the highest sales volume and with five delegations in Latin America (Bank of Spain Archive, Spanish Institute of Foreign Currency, Box 224, Minutes of a Meeting of the Board of Directors, January, 14th, 1966). The proposal for the restructuring of the INLE itself (a reorganization of the services it provided and the restructuring of its legal regime) was the work of a group formed by the director and secretary of the INLE, the academic José M^a Desantes and publishers Hipólito Escolar and Victor Seix (Bank of Spain Archive, Spanish Institute of Foreign Currency, Box 227, INLE, Minutes of a Meeting of the Board of Directors, May 17th, 1963, Agreement 44/63). The debate centred on the manner of reorganization and the consequences of this for the balance of public administration vs. private sector. These are only a few examples of the quite significant involvement of private publishers in the INLE and their influence on sectoral policy.

This second phase of Government support confirms that State policy regarding book publishing was not a closed plan, in accordance with a preconceived idea and a consistent ideological base. On the contrary, it was a response to the context, a pragmatic attempt

to balance the interests of the regime, the currents or groups of power within it and the demands of the publishing companies. The Franco Government, then, must not be understood as a monolith of homogeneous thinking that was isolated from the country's business fabric.

THE NEW LEGAL AND FISCAL FRAMEWORK

This inclusion into the State organism that controlled the Government's policy on books was one of the two aspects in which collective action came to the fore in the publishers' dealings with the State. The other was the change that was occurring in the legal and fiscal framework. This began to be felt as early as 1946; that is to say, during the period of autarky. The early association of publishers in the National Assembly of Authors, Publishers and Booksellers (1944) was instrumental in the creation of the Book Protection Law of 1946. This law was drafted according to the ideas of the publishers themselves. In particular, many of its measures had been presented in a book published by Gustavo Gili in 1944. However, the law was eventually blocked by bureaucratic obstacles. Although the State was willing to respond to the demands of the publishers, the administration did not know how to put these measures into practice. The confusing regulations of the 1946 law and its application by the entities charged with enforcing it would in the end annul its theoretical benefits (Bank of Spain Archive, Spanish Institute of Foreign Currency, INLE Boxes 244 & 227).

At the beginning of the 1960s, the Law of 1946 had still barely been applied, due to its various bureaucratic entanglements, and the publishers found themselves without a legal framework to protect them. At that same time, however, they would see an opportunity in the change that was then taking place in the Government's economic policy, aimed at the country's complete industrialization. From within the INLE, the leading publishers in Madrid and in Catalonia demanded a reform of the Book Protection Law of 1946 and requested that this be included in the Franco Government's new plans. The called-for reforms were articulated through various instruments of economic policy. Two laws in particular had a central role in this process: the Industries of Preferential Interest Law of 2 December 1963; and the Development Plans (the first arising from Law 194/1963, on 28 December). In reality, the plans represented a step backward in the liberal trend marked by the Stabilization Plan, as they involved strong Government intervention. It was the State that would direct the country's investment and production.

The publishing industry was declared as being of preferential interest in December 1963 (Industrial Credit Bank, BBVA Historical Archive, Archive Credit concession policies).

Articles 16^a and 17^a of Law 1964/1963 of 28 December, by which the Social Development Plan for the period 1964-1967 was created, classified the publishing industry as a priority sector for the concession of official credit. The terms under which such assistance had to be given were developed by the Ministry de Finance on 23 July 1964, and by the Ministry of Information and Tourism on 26 November, 1964. After granting this priority classification, however, the Government did not create a new law for the publishing sector. A series of decrees published between the years 1963 and 1971 would for all purposes annul the law of 1946, which nevertheless remained officially in effect (General Administration Archive, Culture Section, Box 73-000475). These were a collection of norms intended to solve the problems of the earlier period regarding the importation of paper, tax exemption for utilities, tax write-offs for exports, the facilitation of financing and reforms in export insurance policies. There is no doubt that the Spanish administration was reacting to pressure from the publishers by establishing norms aimed at facilitating the transformation of the entire Spanish publishing sector.

One of the most beneficial measures for the industry was that of giving tax write-offs for exported products. It consisted of the Tax Office returning all or part of the indirect taxes levied on publishers in the processes of production and sale of exported books. The INLE worked together with the Directorate General of Customs to effect these write-offs for its members. The amounts received by publishers exporting under the licences granted by INLE membership are shown in the following table:

Table 2
Fiscal write-offs for exportation, publishing sector

(in pesetas)

Year	Amount of write-off
1963	61,354,438
1964	82,283,577
1965	86,444,958
1966	96,248,261
1967	95,641,523
1968	266,358,057
1969	335,866,630
1970	354,881,128

Source: Cedán Pazos (1972), p. 214.

The growth in these figures beginning in 1968 was due to the application of another new measure. The Legislative Decree of 30 November, 1967 established that the tax write-off for exported books would be 9% of the total value exported, plus an additional 2% for pertaining to an industry included in the Development Plans.

The principal advantage derived from the sector's being declared priority or preferential was the ease with which credit could be obtained on advantageous terms, Law 2/1962 on the Bases for the Ordering of Credit and Banking. This preferential financing is made evident in two specific figures: exportation credit; and priority credit. The central component in this peculiar banking system was the Industrial Credit Bank (BCI, by its acronym in Spanish). From the BCI, the publishing sector would receive substantial loans with favourable terms, even disproportionate to its weight in the country's total industrial output, as can be observed in the table below:

Table 3

Comparison of percentages of BCI loans granted to each sector in relation to the percentage of their participation in the general industrial production in 1962, 1966 and 1969.

INDUSTRY	1962	1966	1969
Extractive	0.63	2.76	3.05
Food and beverages	0.39	0.23	0.36
Textiles	1.33	0.35	0.43
Footwear	-	0.21	0.85
Wood, Cork and Furniture	0.65	0.5	0.41
<i>Paper, Publishing and Printing</i>	<i>1.16</i>	<i>1.23</i>	<i>1.69</i>
Non-metallic Minerals	3.28	2.01	0.89
Mechanical Metals	1.16	2.31	2.05

Source: Tortella and Jiménez (1986), p. 147. Note: A figure higher than the unit indicates that the BCI loaned to this sector a proportion higher than its weight in the industrial output. If the figure is lower than the unit, loans were proportionately lower than the sector's weight.

The publishers embraced this form of financing *en masse*. For example, in the liabilities of Seix Barral from 1966 to 1968, exportation loans accounted for 8% to 12% of the company's total liabilities. The accounts of Santillana S.A. showed export loans of 4 million pesetas, 4% of total liabilities, with the amounts still rising. From 1968 to 1975, the company's export loans would represent between 5% and 8% of its total liabilities and an average of 17% of current liabilities (Urquijo Bank Archive, Juan March Foundation, Annual Accounts Barral Editores Annual Accounts 1974 and 1976, Editorial Labor Annual Account 1970, Santillana Annual Accounts 1967-1977, and Seix Barral Annual Accounts 1966-1968).

EFFECTS ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

What effect did these measures have on the economic evolution of the publishing sector? They were very positive, especially with regard to internationalization. The graph below traces the evolution of book exports in this period.

Graph 1
Exportation of books (1940-1975)
(in kilogrammes)

Source: *Anuario Estadístico del Comercio Exterior de España*, Ministry of Finance Archive.

The graph enables us to distinguish four periods. The first stage began in 1940 and continued until 1950, and was characterized by very low export figures, as it reflects the harshest years of the post-war period. The second was the decade of the 1950s, when the

historical Spanish publishers, those which already had experience in internationalization before the Civil War, resumed their foreign business dealings. The third period ran from 1960 to 1965 and was a time of higher export figures, thanks to the change in the general political and legal framework. The Stabilization Plan of 1959 not only stabilized and liberalized, but stimulated export activity as well. Within the new framework, the publishers would design individual strategies that, generally speaking, proved to be highly profitable. In 1962, Spain was already the principal provider of the Latin American book sector. Indeed, in that year its exports to Latin America were double that of the second biggest provider, the United States (*El Libro Español*, Jan. 1965, 38-39) However, Spanish publishers also encountered barriers that would slow this foreign growth. One principal problem was that their Mexican and Argentine competitors, companies often founded by exiled Spanish Republicans, were distributing their catalogues throughout the entirety of Latin America. Other barriers included production difficulties from the use of obsolete technology, the high cost of transport (a serious obstacle to international shipping), the difficult and expensive acquisition of quality paper and problems in obtaining credit in a sector which demanded a heavy initial investment but offered a very slow return (Fernández Moya, 2009).

A great many of these problems would be solved by the Government's measures of support for the industry. The fourth period, then, begins with the implementation of these measures in 1963-64. It is clear that the new institutional framework provided strong incentives for internationalization. More than this, the design of the new measures would mark the business strategies of these companies, encouraging exportation rather than other forms of internationalization, such as direct investment with production in the country of destination or the concession of licences for publishing abroad. To maximize fiscal benefits (loans and tax write-offs for exportation), printing had to be done on national soil, which also generated a beneficial carry-over effect for the graphic arts sector. As a result, Spanish publishing exports would skyrocket after the mid-1960s.

In contrast to the official Government statistics, we present below figures from UNESCO regarding publishing output. In the lower table, it can be seen that the great change that was in store for the publishing sector would have to wait until the 1960s. It was then that Spain would take its position among the elite of the international sector.

Table 4

Leading publishing countries, 1937-1973 *Number of book titles*

	1937-39	1940-44	1945-49	1950	1955	1960	1965	1970	1973
United States	10.873	9.452	8.851	11.022	12.589	15.012	54.378	79.530	83.724
Soviet Union	43.348	45.800		43.100	54.732	76.064	76.101	78.899	80.196
Germany, Federal Republic	25.400			14.094	16.660	21.103	25.994	45.369	48.034
Japan	30.732			13.009	21.653	23.682	24.203	31.249	35.857
Great Britain	16.087	7.874	12.585	17.072	19.962	23.783	26.314	33.441	35.177
France	8.124	6.379	10.670	9.993	11.793	11.872	17.138	22.935	27.186
Spain		4.892	3.689	3.633	4.812	6.085	17.342	19.717	23.608
India	24.000	18.740		18.769	18.559	10.741	13.094	14.145	14.064
Netherlands	6.207	3.566	6.177	6.537	7.353	7.893	10.193	11.159	11.640
Poland			4.602	5.218	7.199	7.305	8.509	10.038	10.744

Source: Division of Statistics on Culture and Communication, Office of Statistics, UNESCO.

The main Spanish publishers, both the historical leaders and those of more recent creation but intent on growth, would use these measures to renovate their facilities and to either increase or initiate their expansion into foreign markets. The measures also enabled them to effectively balance their finances, with easy access to credit and subsidies for exportation. The table below shows data on the internationalization processes of the leading Spanish publishers.

Table 5
Ranking of Spanish Publishers, 1975

Company	Type	Ownership	% Exports	Affiliates	Catalogue	Average workers in Spain 1974-1975	Average Turnover in thousand pesetas 1974-1975
Planeta	Newborn firm	Family firm	40%	Mexico, Colombia and Argentina	Literature, best-sellers and encyclopaedias	700	1,235

Salvat Editores	Historical firm	Family firm	60%	Mexico, Buenos Aires, Caracas, Rio de Janeiro and Bogotá; France, Switzerland, Great Britain, Germany and Belgium	Encyclopaedias, large format, fascicles	282	1,115
Bruguera	Newborn firm	Family firm	50%	Mexico, Buenos Aires, Bogotá, Rio de Janeiro	Paperbacks, children's books, magazines and comics for children and young people	1,175	974
Editorial Labor	Historical firm	Family firm	50%	Mexico, Buenos Aires, Caracas, Bogotá, Rio de Janeiro, Quito and Lisbon	Technical books, large format, encyclopaedias	200	710
Plaza y Janés	Newborn firm	Family firm	50%	Mexico, Buenos Aires and Montevideo	Literature, Best-sellers	315	610
Espasa Calpe	Historical firm	Listed company	40%	Mexico and Argentina	Encyclopaedias, large format, literature	427	522
Aguilar	Historical firm	Family firm	50%	Mexico, Buenos Aires, Montevideo and Santiago de Chile	Literature, Best-sellers	505	518
Editorial Ramón Sopena	Historical firm	Family firm	50%	Buenos Aires, Mexico	Encyclopaedias	805	512
Seix Barral	Newborn firm	Family firm	60%	Mexico, Caracas, Bogotá, Quito, Lima, Santiago de Chile and Buenos Aires	Literature		
Santillana	Newborn firm	Family firm	40%	Buenos Aires, Mexico, Chile	Textbooks		

Source: Annual Accounts of Seix Barral, Santillana, Editorial Labor, Aguilar, Editorial Labor; *Anuario Financiero y de Sociedades Anónimas* 1950, 1955, 1960, 1965, 1970 and 1975; Fomento de Producción . Urquijo Bank Archive, Gustavo Gili, Salvat, Espasa Calpe

Archives. Newborn is a company founded during Franco regime. Historical firm is a company founded before the Spanish Civil War of 1936.

As we are witnessing here, the measures did not create a new sector, but rather gave economic support to an industry that was already internationalized but had certain barriers to increasing its presence in foreign markets. If we compare the situation of the Spanish publishing industry to that of other publishing sectors, we are able to analyse how these measures affected international competitiveness. The Spanish publishers began to produce in better conditions than those of their Mexican, Argentine or Chilean counterparts, which allowed them to offer competitive prices in Latin American markets. The financial strength of the Spanish publishers was also an advantage for competing with local companies when the Latin American economic crises of the 1970s hit.

If we put the case of Spain into a European perspective, we can affirm that these measures allowed the concentration that faced Spanish publishers to be delayed. The process of concentration itself began in Europe in the late 1960s. The publishing sector was already quite mature, with low growth rates and limited profit margins that demanded an increase in sales volume. The formation of large publishing groups permitted companies to exploit synergies and economies of scale where possible. In 1968, in Germany, nineteen publishers were doing business of 5 to 50 million DM, while fifty-six others had turnovers of 50,000 to 500,000 DM (Fernandez Moya, 2012). In the mid-1960s, the turnover of nineteen French companies represented 54.2 percent of the total sector total in that country, while that of 192 small publishing houses was barely 7.3 percent (*El Libro Español*, Mar. 1975, 103-104). In Spain, the process of concentration would not begin until the mid-1980s. Meanwhile, in the 1960s and 70s, the measures taken would provide the publishers with sufficient financial support, and it would thus be unnecessary to pursue efficiency through mergers and acquisitions or the creation of economies of scale in order to reduce costs.

CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this article was to examine the development of Spanish capitalism under Franco's dictatorship (1939-1975) through the interaction between two major players: the book publishing industry, a fast growing and internationally minded industry, and the Spanish Government. Based on extensive empirical data, we argue that Spanish book publishers, by defending their interests and redefining their strategies strengthened their coordinating capacities on two levels: within the publishing industry and with the many

governmental bodies that regulated their business activity. Ultimately, these capacities contributed to shape Spain’s economic policy and institutions in a crucial period for the modernization of Spain.

The findings of this study are summarized in Table 6. The basic idea of the theory of varieties of capitalism argues that a certain institutional framework, by establishing the rules of the game, encouraged cooperative behavior among companies, in case the of CMEs, or prevent it, in the case of LMEs (Hall and Soskice, 2001). In our case study, a predatory State limited autonomy of movement for entrepreneurs, reducing their capacity to react against its abuses. Cooperative behaviors were theoretically hindered by an official framework which offer one single channel: “Vertical Unions”, and conceded very little freedom to the existing business organizations. Notwithstanding, over and above the official framework, the entrepreneurs found ways to cooperate and defend their interest, thanks to informal networks and corporatist practices. Under the leadership from historical firms, publishers transformed the existing trade associations into coalition tools. New entrants soon joined this proactive group.

Table 6.

Interests, strategies, instruments and institutional outcome of Government-publishers interaction under Franco’s dictatorship.

	Autarchic Period (1939-1957)	Developmental Period (1957-1975)
Government	Seeks ideological control and protectionist framework through: Spanish Book National Institute (INLE) 1939 Censorship 1939 Editora Nacional 1941 Book Protection Law 1946	Seeks domestic and international legitimation and more efficient management of rising publishing activity and book demand through: Technocratic shift 1957 Preferential Interest Law 1963 Press Law 1966 Tax and financial incentives decree 1967
Publishers	Seek to keep domestic and international markets and pre-war trade guilds, engaging in new institutions	Seek to maximize impact of domestic technocratic shift and worldwide publishing boom influencing regulatory framework.

	and limiting the damage of new regulatory framework.	
Institutional Outcome	Book publishing becomes tightly regulated and ideologically controlled but private firms and pre-war trade guilds survive and historical leaders retain some influence in new regulatory bodies (but fail to fully shape 1946 Law).	Leading historical and new book publishers increase their formal and informal influence in INLE and new legal framework, which provides extensive tax and financial incentives to private publishing firms. Dramatic domestic and international growth of Spanish book publishing.

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

It is important to note that Franco's Government did not develop a defined, coherent and structured book publishing policy. Despite the strong ideological dimension of the post-war institutions, this article shows that Spain's book policy was dictated by the evolving interests and strategies of Government and entrepreneurs, and the imperatives of economic growth and national and international legitimacy. This bidirectional process was necessarily pragmatic. The coordination capacities developed throughout the process by private publishers and public administrators ended up transforming the institutional arrangements of Spanish capitalism. In sort, this is not a typical case study of lobbies. It was a dictatorial Government in the middle of an institutional change, which dialogued with the entrepreneurs, and invited them to participate in the process. They were active players in the elaboration of the new measures and even in their implementation, from their leading positions in the institutions. Publishing was not the only industry subsidized by the State, many sectors were financially supported to foster a rapid industrialization of the country. This is how the regime managed the transformation of Spain from an agrarian to an industrial economy during our observation period.

What does this article add to the VoC debate? First, the research findings explained here are consistent with previous literature about Spanish VoC. Preceding works, mostly focused on Spanish economic development during the democracy (1975-2018), demonstrated that Spanish capitalism is based on coordination, coalitions, and corporatism (Royo, 2002, 2007). Our paper shows that, even in a dictatorship, during a period of liberalization (after 1959), when the international context and Spanish openness increased convergence with liberal models, informal networks and corporatist bargaining, two typical non- market mechanisms, coordinated economic activity.

Second, the Spanish experience related in these pages challenges the classic interpretation in several aspects. We have attempted to reveal that the institutional fabric of national economic and social models can change over time, even in authoritarian regimes with highly intervened markets. The VoC debate was born as an ahistorical theoretical debate, nonetheless the question of why and how change takes place requires detailed historical analysis. In this sense, the Spanish case is extremely relevant because it allows us to study a deep institutional change within that same dictatorial regime. Our historical analysis illustrates that the State is a dynamic entity with significant adaptation and coordination capacities. The research reveals that institutional change is not always the consequence of an exogenous shock, but the result of a more complex process. What dynamics and actors played a role in this transformation? Our study states that firms and entrepreneurs, whose role is undervalued in the proposal of Hall and Soskice (2001), are active and pragmatic actors capable of and motivated to modify the existing rules of the game through stable industrial coalitions as well as through ad-hoc coordination with governmental institutions. We have made the point that the theory of institutional determinism is insufficient to understand institutional change. Institutional evolution and adaptation seem to be the result of the actions of different actors with particular incentives and interests.

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